

Characterization of Multi-walled Carbon Nanotube / Thermosetting Polyimide Composites

Toshio Ogasawara, Yuichi Ishida, and Takashi Ishikawa
National Aerospace Laboratory of Japan (NAL)
6-13-1, Osawa, Mitaka-shi, Tokyo, 181-0015, JAPAN

Rikio Yokota
Institute of Space and Astronautical Science (ISAS)
3-1-1, Yoshinodai, Sagamihara-shi, Kanagawa, 229-8510, Japan

SUMMARY: Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MW-CNTs) were dispersed throughout a thermosetting polyimide "Triple A PI" (TriA-PI)". TriA-PI is a newly developed phenylethynyl terminated polyimide, and exhibits excellent mechanical properties and processability with high glass transition temperature ($T_g > 300^\circ\text{C}$). The resulting composites containing 3.3, 7.7, 14.3 wt% MW-CNT exhibited relatively good dispersion in macroscopic scale. Tensile tests on the composites showed an increase in the elastic modulus and the yield strength, and decrease in the failure strain. Dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA) showed an increase in the glass transition temperature with incorporation of the carbon nanotubes. The experimental result suggested that the carbon nanotubes are acting as macroscopic crosslinks, and are further immobilizing the polyimide chains at elevated temperature.

KEYWORDS: polyimide, carbon nanotube, glass transition temperature, dynamic mechanical analysis,

INTRODUCTION

Since the first TEM observation by Iijima [1], many researchers reported the remarkable physical and mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanofibers (CNFs). It has been reported that the mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes exceed those of any existing materials. For example, the theoretical elastic modulus is greater than 1 TPa, and the reported tensile strengths exceed 50 GPa [2,3,4]. Furthermore, the cost of CNT has been drastically decreasing, because many companies have been devoting a great amount of efforts for development of the mass production. If the cost of CNTs will be on the downward trend, CNTs will be no longer special materials in the near future.

It has been expected that the carbon nanotubes and nanofibers could yield excellent reinforcement in polymer composites [4]. There has been recent interest in the development of CNT based polymer composites. The effects of CNT or CNF addition on the mechanical, thermal and electrical properties have been investigated for various kinds of thermoplastic polymers such as polypropylene [5], polystyrene (PS) [6], poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) [7,8,9], nylon 12, and poly ether ether ketone (PEEK) [10], and the increases in strength, elastic modulus, and electrical conductivity have been found. For thermosetting polymers, some researchers investigated the properties of CNT/epoxy composites, and the increases in elastic modulus, electrical conductivity, and glass transition temperature with CNT addition were reported [11,12]. However,

CNT / thermosetting polyimide composites have not been reported.

Thermosetting polyimides have been attempted to apply composite matrix and adhesive for aircraft structures and turbo fan engine components. Especially, the phenylethynyl terminated polyimide designated PETI-5 is one of the most excellent thermosetting polyimides for use as a composite matrix and adhesive. PETI-5 was developed in NASA Langley Research Center, and exhibits excellent mechanical properties, solvent resistance, acceptable processability, and high glass transition temperature of 270°C [13, 14]. It has been believed that PETI-5 is the most excellent thermosetting polyimide.

Recently, a new phenylethynyl terminated imide oligomer was developed using asymmetric 2, 3, 3', 4'- biphenyltetracarboxylic dianhydride (a-BPDA) [15,16]. The polyimides are referred to as Triple-A PI (Tri-A PI) from the characteristic of the polymer, amorphous, asymmetric, and addition type. The cured polymer exhibits higher glass transition temperature (T_g) as compared with PETI-5 synthesized from the symmetric 3,3,4',4'-biphenyltetracarboxylic dianhydride (s-BPDA). Because of the catenation from the dianhydride, the Tri-A polyimides have highly irregular structures resulting in lower melting temperature, and cured polymer exhibits higher T_g as compared with PETI-5.

In this study, the multi walled CNT / Tri-A PI composites containing 0, 3.3, 7.7, and 14.3 wt% CNTs were fabricated, and the properties were characterized by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA) and tensile tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Starting Materials

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MW-CNTs) synthesized by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process were obtained from Carbon Nanotech Research Institute (CNRI) Inc. which is a subsidiary of Mitsui Corporation (Tokyo, Japan). Figure 1 shows an scanning electron micrograph illustrating the MW-CNTs with the diameters in the range of 20-100 nm, and average length of a few hundreds micrometers. The nanotubes are highly entangled and randomly oriented. According to X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) for the as-received CNTs, C=O and C-O-C were detected as well as C-C and C=C bonds. It suggests that the surfaces of the CNTs were slightly oxidized.

The imide oligomers used in this study were obtained from UBE Industries Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan). The following chemicals were used without further purification: 4, 4'-oxydianiline (4,4'-ODA) 2, 3, 3', 4'-biphenyltetracarboxylic dianhydride (a-BPDA), 4-phenyl ethynyl phthalic anhydride (PEPA) and N-methyl 1-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP). The imide oligomer was prepared at a calculated molecular weight (Mw) of 1560 g/mole for the imide segment by reacting a-BPDA with 4, 4'-ODA and endcapping with PEPA as shown in Fig. 2. The 4, 4'-ODA was dissolved in NMP at room temperature under nitrogen, and then the dianhydride and endcapper were added. The reactions were allowed to stir for ~24 hrs at ambient temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere. The amide acid solution was thermally imidized at 180°C for 2 hours, and then the soluble oligomer was recovered by precipitation in water and washed in acetone. The powder was dried at 100°C in air.

2.2 Composite preparation

CNTs / imide oligomer mixtures containing 0, 3.3, 7.7, and 14.3 wt% CNTs were prepared using a mechanical blender without any solution (dry condition) for several minutes. The volume fraction of CNTs are calculated to be 2.3, 5.4, 10.3 vol% from the density of the CNTs (1.9 g/cm³) and the cured polyimide (1.7g/cm³). Particle size of the imide oligomers was in the range of 0.1-10 μm, and CNTs were not dispersed uniformly in the mixture. The loss of aspect ratio during the mechanical blending was not observed remarkably, therefore the CNTs were flexible for mechanical blend process with the imide oligomers. The CNT / imide oligomer mixture was melted at 320°C for 10 minutes on a steel plate in a hot press, and then cured at 370°C for 1 hour under 0.2 MPa of pressure with PTFE spacer (thickness 1 mm).

2.3 Characterizations

The CNT dispersion of the composites was observed using optical and scanning electron microscopes. In order to characterize the thermomechanical properties, the composites with different nanotube concentrations were tested with a dynamic mechanical thermal analyzer (DMA). A TA Instruments Q800 was used in the single cantilever beam test mode with 17.5 mm span length, 5mm width, and 1mm thick. The tests were run from 30°C to 450°C at 3 °C/min with cycling rate of 1 Hz, and strain of 0.1 %.

Tensile tests were conducted on a servo-hydraulic testing machine (Model 8501, Instron, USA) under the constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min at room temperature. GFRP end tabs (20mm length, 2mm thick) were bonded on both sides of the grip portions. Specimen size was 1 mm thick, 5 mm width, and 80 mm overall length, and three specimens were prepared for each CNT concentration. Longitudinal strain was measured using a contact type extensometer (Instron, USA) with gage length of 12.5 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Microscopic observations

Figure 3 (a) and (b) show optical micrographs of the composites containing 3.3 and 14.3 wt. % of CNTs, respectively. The CNTs just below the surfaces were observed through the transparent polyimide under dark image field. Figure 4 (a) and (b) are SEM photographs illustrating the CNT dispersion of the 14.3 % CNT composite under the

acceleration electron voltage of 20 kV. It was impossible to observe the CNT dispersion using an SEM except the 14.3 % CNT composite, because of significant charge-up.

The CNT dispersion in the composites was similar to that in the CNT / imide oligomer mixture, which suggests that uniform dispersion of CNTs in the CNT / imide oligomer mixture is important to make well dispersed composites. It seemed that the dispersed CNTs formed secondary network structures with sub-micron-order in addition to primary crosslink structure made of the polyimide.

3.2 Dynamic mechanical properties

Three kinds of information can be obtained from DMA: the storage modulus E' , the loss modulus E'' , and the $\tan \delta$. The typical DMA curves are shown in Figures 5, and the glass transition temperatures (T_g) defined as the onset temperature of decrease in the storage modulus E' were listed in Table 1. The estimated glass transition temperatures are 335, 339, 350, 357°C for the 0, 3.3, 7.7, 14.3 wt.% MW-CNTs / Tri-A PI composites, respectively. The increase in the glass transition temperature was hardly observed for carbon fiber reinforced / Tri-A PI composites [17], therefore, the increase is a particular phenomenon for the CNT / Tri-A PI composites. The experimental results indicate that there is significant interaction between the polyimide and the MW-CNTs. It was supposed that secondary network structure was formed by the nanotubes in addition to the primary crosslink structure of the polymers, and CNTs are immobilizing polymer chains at elevated temperature. Another explanation is that the thermosetting polymers are covalently bonding to functional groups on the surface of the MW-CNTs. The similar experimental results were reported for nitrogen doped multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CN_x -MWNT) / epoxy composites, and a 20°C increase in the T_g was observed by 2.5 wt.% of CN_x -MWNT dispersion [12].

On the other hand, it was reported that T_g was not affected by CNT dispersion for PEEK [10]. These experimental results suggest that cross-linked network structure affects increase in glass transition temperature. However, the effects of CNT radius and surface chemicals can't be ignored, the detailed mechanism was not revealed in detail

from the experimental results. Although the surfaces of CNTs were slightly oxidized,

the chemical reaction between phenylethynyl group and CNTs has not been understood at present. According to SEM observation afterwards, any pulled-out CNTs were observed after tensile testing. This suggests that the chemical bonding between the nanotubes and the polymer is not significant.

Table 1 Properties of the MW-CNT/Tri A-PI composites

CNT (wt%)	CNT (vol %)	Tg * (°C)	E ** (GPa)	σ_{uts} (MPa)	ϵ_{max} (%)	$\sigma_{0.2}$ (MPa)
0	0	335	2.84	115.6	7.6	69.8
3.3	2.3	339	3.07	99.5	4.0	80.5
7.7	5.4	350	3.28	97.6	3.6	84.6
14.3	10.3	357	3.90	95.2	2.6	92.6

* Onset temperature of decreasing in storage modulus (DMA)

** Strain range of 0.5-1.0 % (Tensile testing)

3.3 Tensile properties

The stress / strain curves are shown in Figure 6, and the average tensile properties such as elastic modulus E, yield stress $\sigma_{0.2}$ (0.2% strain), ultimate tensile strength σ_{uts} , and failure strain ϵ_{max} are summarized in Table 1. The ultimate tensile strengths and Young's moduli are also shown in Figures 7 and 8 as a function of CNT concentration. The initial elastic modulus of each specimen was calculated between 0.5 and 1.0 % of strain. Compared with the base polymer, an addition of CNTs results in increases in the

elastic modulus and the yield strength, and decrease in the failure strain.

However, an increase in the elastic modulus was not significant, e.g. 37% for 14.3wt% of CNT addition. Qian et al. characterized MW-CNT / polystyrene (PS) composites with the addition of 1 wt%, and achieved about 36-42 % increase in the elastic modulus and a 25% increase in the tensile strength [6]. They estimated the elastic modulus of the composites using an in-plane random oriented discontinuous fiber lamina model, and reported that the estimated elastic moduli were only 10% higher than that the experimental data [9]. The elastic moduli were calculated using the

same model, and the results were superimposed in Figure 8 for CNT elastic modulus, E_{CNT} of 20, 200, and 500 GPa, respectively. Although the best fit elastic modulus of CNT was obtained to be 20 GPa, this value is much lower than the values reported for isolated carbon nanotubes [2,3]. Therefore, it was supposed that the in-plane random oriented fiber model is not adequate for this composite system, and the effect of the three-dimensional random orientation and entangled distribution of the nanotubes should be taken into consideration. An alternative explanation is that the stress transfer between the matrix and the nanotube is weak because of sliding between tube interfaces in MW-CNTs.

Fracture strain decreases with CNT concentration, which is not only caused by increase in the elastic modulus but also the heterogeneous CNT dispersion. For example, SEM micrographs illustrating the fracture surfaces of the 14.3 wt% CNT composite after tensile testing are shown in Figures 9. It seems that the fracture origin is the CNT aggregation. Therefore, the ultimate tensile strengths of the composites can be improved by making the nanotube dispersion uniform.

CONCLUSION

In this study, Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MW-CNTs) were dispersed throughout a thermosetting polyimide "Triple A PI" (TriA-PI). TriA-PI is a newly developed phenylethynyl terminated polyimide, and exhibits excellent mechanical properties and processability with high glass transition temperature ($T_g > 300^\circ\text{C}$). The resulting composites containing 3.3, 7.7, 14.3 wt% MW-CNT exhibited relatively good dispersion. Tensile tests on the composites showed an increase in the elastic modulus and the yield strength, and decrease in the failure strain. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) showed an increase in the glass transition temperature with incorporation of the MW-CNTs. The experimental result suggested that the MW-CNTs are acting as

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Iijima, "Helical microtubules of graphitic carbon", *Nature*, 354 (1991), 56-58
- [2] J-P. Salventat, G. A. D. Briggs, J-M. Bonard, R. R. Bacsá, A. J. Kulik, T. Stockli, N. A. Burnham, and L. Forro, "Elastic and shear moduli of single-walled carbon nanotubes ropes", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 82 [5] (1999), 944-947
- [3] M-F. Yu, B. S. Files, S. Arepalli, and R. S. Ruoff, "Tensile Loading of Ropes of Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes and their Mechanical Properties", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 84 [24], (2000), 5552-5555
- [4] E. T. Thostenson, Z. Ren, and T-W. Chou, "Advances in the science and technology of carbon nanotubes and their composites: a review", *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, 61 (2001), 1899-1912
- [5] S. A. Gordeyev, F. J. Macedo, J. A. Ferreira, F. W. J. van Hattum, and C. C. Bernardo, Transport properties of polymer-vapour grown carbon fibre composites, *Physica B*, 279 (2000), 33-36
- [6] D. Qian, E. Co. Dickey, R. Andrews, T. Rantell, "Load transfer and deformation mechanisms in carbon nanotubes-polystyrene composites", *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 76, 20 (2000), 2868-2870
- [7] Z. Jia, Z. Wang, C. Xu, J. Liang, B. Wei, D. Wu, and S. Zhu, "Study on poly(methyl methacrylate)/carbon nanotube composites", *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, A271 (1999), 395-400
- [8] C. Stephan, T. P. Nguyen, M. L. de la Chapelle, S. Lefrant, C. Journet, and P. Bernier, "Characterization of singlewalled carbon nanotubes-PMMA composites", *Synthetic Metals*, 108 (2000), 139-149
- [9] C. A. Cooper, D. Ravich, D. Lips, J. Mayer, and H. D. Wagner, "Distribution and alignment of carbon nanotubes and nanofibrils in a polymer matrix", *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, 62 (2002), 1105-1112
- [10] J. Sandler, P. Werner, M. S. P. Shaffer, V. Demchuk, V. Altstadt, A. H. Windle, "Carbon-nanofibre-reinforced poly(ether ether ketone) composites", *Composite: Part A*, 33, (2002), 1033-1039
- [11] A. Allaoui, S. Bai, H. M. Cheng, and J. B. Bai, "Mechanical and electrical properties of a MWNT/epoxy composite", *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, 62 (2002), 1993-1998
- [12] A. Eitan, L. S. Schadler, J. Hansen, P. M. Ajayan, R. W. Siegel, M. Terrones, M. Grobert, M. Reyes-Reyes, M. Mayne and H. Terrones, "Processing and thermal characterization of nitrogen doped MWNT/Epoxy composites", Proc. 10th US-Japan conference on composite materials (2002) 634-640
- [13] P. M. Hergenrother, and J. G. Smith, Jr, *Polymer*, 35(22), 4857 (1994)
- [14] P. M. Hergenrother, "Development of Composites, Adhesives and Sealants for High-Speed Commercial Airplanes", *SAMPE Journal*, 36 [1], 30-41 (2000)
- [15] R. Yokota, S. Yamamoto S. Yano, T. Sawaguchi, M. Hasegawa, H. Yamaguchi, H. Ozawa, and R. Sato, "Molecular design of heat resistant polyimides having

- excellent processability and high glass transition temperature," *High Performance Polymers*, 13, S61-S72 (2001)
- [16] R. Yokota, S. Yamamoto S. Yano, T. Sawaguchi, M. Hasegawa, H. Yamaguchi, H. Ozawa, and R. Sato, "Novel phenylethynyl-terminated asymmetric BPDA based polyimides having excellent processability and thermo-oxidative stability," *Polyimides and Other High Temperature Polymers*, 1, 101-111 (2001)
- [17] T. Ogasawara, T. Ishikawa, R. Yokota, H. Ozawa, M. Taguchi, Y. Shigenari, and K. Miyagawa," Processing and properties of carbon fiber reinforced Triple-A polyimide (Tri-A PI) matrix composites", *Adv. Comp. Mater.*, 11 [3] (2002), 277-286